

LASER REMOVAL OF RAC COATING FROM COMPOSITE MATERIAL SURFACES

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ABSTRACT

Physical polishing, chemical removal and laser removal are three well-known methods to remove RAM (radar absorbing material) coatings from composite substrates. Their removal efficiency and effects on substrate properties are compared in this paper. Although thin RAM coatings ($\leq 100\mu\text{m}$) can be completely removed by all three methods, the exposed substrate materials exhibit various mechanical properties. While the physical polishing and chemical paint remover methods barely impact the tensile and flexural properties of the composite substrates, the laser removal method imposes a significant influence. Resins on the surface of the substrate composites partially evaporate with coatings under laser beam, and the average length of fibers decreases due to laser frying. It is suggested that the laser removal technique deteriorates the mechanical properties of the composite substrate after coating removal.

1 INTRODUCTION

Applications of composite materials in aviation field have been increasingly focused. Composite materials are usually coated to enhance the durability, corrosion resistance, and oxidation resistance and so on. Since coatings inevitably undergo degradation during service, coating repair is necessary. The first step of repair is to remove the original coatings from the substrates, fully or partially. Coating removal process first requires simplicity and economy. Second, the surface should be clean and free of residue after removal. More importantly, the structural integrity of the composite substrates must be maintained during removal process in order to ensure future practice.

Common coating removal techniques include mechanical polishing, chemical removal, high-pressure water jet removal and so on, all of which have advantages and disadvantages. Physical polishing process is done by manually grinding, which means low efficiency and low success rate,

depending on the productiveness of the technicians. Chemical removal show obvious effect and it is suitable for large area except paint job. However, the shortcomings of this method include difficulty in controlling accuracy and toxicity. In comparison, high pressure water jet is advantageous for large-area paint removal but still suffers from accuracy. Recently, laser removal technique has been developed as a more advanced method for local fixed-site coating removal; it is barely toxic and is particularly suitable for precision coating removal at a small area. However, high expense and low efficiency on large-area-removal have hindered its application. As a new process for coating removal, it has big advantage compared with other methods, by updating and adjusting the parameters of the device, the laser removal process could be suitable for large area coating removal which is one of the main directions of the current study.

In this paper, radar absorbing coating (RAC) was chosen as a removable object. The RAC is a special function coating, which contains large amounts of metal powders and has higher solid content than other coatings. Laser removal process is more demanding because the metal powders inside RAC will absorb a lot of laser energy during the coating removal process. If RAC can be successfully removed by laser, this method is also applicable to the removal of other coating. In order to characterize the laser removal process influence on composite substrate, physical polishing, chemical paint remover paint removal processes were carried on. In this paper, coating removal effects of three methods were compared, and mechanical properties and surface morphology of composite substrate after paint removal processes were tested.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The substrate material used in this study is carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite with a thickness of 2.00 mm. CCF300 carbon fiber was purchased from Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co., LTD and 5228A epoxy resin was obtained from AVIC Composite Corporation LTD.

RAC with a thickness of 50 μ m was sprayed on the surface of composite substrates. After the coating was cured completely, three different types of techniques were utilized to achieve the removal of coating, namely mechanical polishing, chemical corrosion with paint remover, and laser removal.

Mechanical polishing, which refers to the manual polishing with the assistance of sandpaper with 400 grits, was conducted until the composite substrates exposed. Acid paint remover (TQ-1) obtained from Beijing Xindaxin Corp. was employed in the chemical stripping method. The remover was brushed on the whole surface of the coating uniformly, hence coating was infiltrated in the remover completely. The process keeps for 4 hours to guarantee the completely thorough cleaning of the coating. Laserblast 1000 manufactured by Quantel Co. (France) was utilized to produce the laser as required, while the ablation power and wavelength were set as 36W and 160Hz respectively. During the process of ablation, laser emission spot was moved on the composite surface at an even speed back and forth.

Tensile properties and flexural properties of the materials were measured following ASTM D3039 and ASTM D790 standards. Scanning electron microscopy (FEI, Quanta 600, USA) was utilized to examine the surface morphology.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 presents the appearance of composites before the removal of radar absorbing coating and after removal of the coating with three different cleaning methods. The initial radar absorbing coating exhibits dark gray with a flat surface. When the coating was removed by physical polishing, the original black background of composite was restored. What's more, surface becomes much more flat and smooth, even with mirror gloss. This was attributed to the continuous polishing effect. In the circumstance of chemical stripping, the composite recovers to original black as well. However, there is no mirror gloss being observed, indicting relatively strong corrosion effect. After the coating was removed by laser ablation, the surface of composite becomes apparently rougher with the trace of laser movement. This is mainly due to the deviation of laser movement direction caused by manual control. Laser may stay at some positions for longer time randomly, leading to a much more server ablation at these sites, eventually resulting in uneven surface condition.

Figure 1: Appearance of the coated and stripped composite materials: a, untreated. b, mechanical polishing. c, chemical removal. d, Laser removal

SEM was employed to observe the microscopic morphology of these four materials, as presented in Figure 2, with the magnification of 800X. As seen in Fig. 1(a), original composite substrate was composed of woven fabric, and the fiber was aligned orderly. After the radar absorbing coating was polished physically, the trace of polishing could be observed obviously, and fibers were still impregnated in epoxy matrix, as shown in Fig. 2(b). Fig. 2(c) represents the surface condition of composite after removal of radar absorbing coating by chemical stripping with assistance of paint remover. There were plenty of residues on the surface, which was aroused from the swelling effect of epoxy matrix by interacting with acid paint remover. Surface morphology of composite utilizing laser ablation removal technique was shown in Fig. 2(d). Epoxy resin on the surface was ablated out entirely, and the fiber, which was originally impregnated in the resin matrix, became totally neat. Furthermore, a considerable proportion of fiber was burned in two, indicating the power and wavelength of the laser have not been adjusted to appropriate levels. In summary, the composite substrate was damaged during the laser ablation process.

Figure 2: microscopic morphology of composite surface with different removal methods: a, untreated. b, mechanical polishing. c, chemical removal. d, Laser removal

The tensile strengths and tensile modulus of as-obtained four materials were listed in Table 1 and Table 2, and flexural strengths and flexural modulus were listed in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively. Tensile strength and tensile modulus of composite employing physical polishing removal technique were 1340MPa and 120GPa, almost the same as the situation for original composite, of which tensile strength and tensile modulus were measured as 1370 MPa and 120GPa respectively. Similarly, composite using chemical stripping method gave close values as original composite. However, for laser treated composite, the tensile strength dropped from 1370MPa to 1270MPa, while tensile modulus remained basically unchanged.

Flexural properties of these four materials tend to vary similarly to tensile properties. Coating removal techniques, including both physical polishing and chemical stripping, seemed to have little influence on the flexural strength and modulus of the composite, while laser ablation removal technique would lead to decreased flexural properties.

serial	tensile strengths [MPa]			
	untreated	mechanical polishing	chemical removal	Laser removal
1	1329.26	1335.41	1464.16	1366.32
2	1395.82	1447.98	1406.51	1327.48
3	1399.78	1485.34	1268.42	1239.29
4	1318.03	1230.69	1503.37	1156.06
5	1439.86	1417.12	1404.67	1191.68
6	1343.01	1205.20	1458.73	1320.42
7	1333.83	1194.65	1505.84	1369.92
8	1414.66	1442.33	1447.10	1192.88
Average value	1371.78	1344.84	1432.35	1270.51

Table 1: Tensile strengths of composite specimen with different removal methods

serial	tensile modulus [GPa]			
	untreated	mechanical polishing	chemical removal	Laser removal
1	119.19	115.68	119.56	131.91
2	123.68	118.76	126.69	122.34
3	119.89	123.73	123.32	127.75
4	110.36	124.62	116.21	131.94
5	113.60	117.83	119.17	124.46
6	119.39	117.70	126.69	132.40
7	134.73	124.75	117.75	131.38

8	118.96	120.28	125.67	138.58
Average value	119.98	120.42	121.88	130.10

Table 2: Tensile modulus of composite specimen with different removal methods

serial	flexural strength [MPa]			
	untreated	mechanical polishing	chemical removal	Laser removal
1	1693.66	1712.22	1602.41	1419.34
2	1649.34	1535.56	1838.01	1448.79
3	1730.06	1570.05	1603.43	1501.60
4	1644.46	1702.33	1703.51	1448.31
5	1687.21	1902.46	1645.05	1546.03
6	1561.54	1867.20	1657.27	1392.46
7	1719.10	1839.10	1655.00	1527.00
8	1692.03	1640.36	1664.11	1504.51
Average value	1672.18	1721.16	1671.10	1473.51

Table 3: Flexural strength of composite specimen with different removal methods

serial	flexural modulus [GPa]			
	untreated	mechanical polishing	chemical removal	Laser removal
1	136.42	122.72	127.61	112.89
2	124.75	118.17	140.76	117.38
3	134.45	123.50	122.25	120.32
4	124.10	123.88	132.46	114.54
5	127.57	116.77	126.95	116.46
6	120.39	123.28	127.70	116.65
7	136.80	132.00	126.61	118.42
8	127.66	124.78	127.57	127.28
Average value	129.02	123.14	128.99	117.99

Table 4: Flexural modulus of composite specimen with different removal methods

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work has studied the effectiveness of three well-known methods to remove RAM (radar absorbing material) coatings of 50-80 μ m in thickness from CF/EP composite substrates. Physical polishing and chemical removal methods barely impact the tensile and flexural properties of the composite substrates. It has been shown that the coatings were removed effectively by laser removal, yet causing substantial damage to composite substrates. Resins on the surface of the substrate composites partially evaporate with coatings under laser beam, and the average length of fibers decreases due to laser frying. Mechanical tests have indicated that the tensile and flexural properties declined: tensile strength and flexural strength decreased by 7% and 11%, respectively. It is suggested that the laser removal technique deteriorates the mechanical properties of the composite substrate after coating removal.

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